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6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
Facility

Deliverable D2.2

Final overall framework design and
requirements

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable refines and finalizes the framework and requirements for the 6G-SANDBOX Facility, building on the foundation established in D2.1. It specifies the functional and non-functional requirements of architectural components and presents a comprehensive design for the facility. Additionally, it updates the architecture of the project's four platforms, incorporating advancements (extensions) from Open Calls (OCs) supported by the project.

The deliverable is organized into five chapters: an introduction, requirements report, the finalized overall architecture, the updated architecture of the four platforms, and a concluding summary. Its target audiences include the project consortium, the research community, funding agencies, technology providers, and the public. The structure and the overall content ensure validation of objectives, alignment among stakeholders, and transparency in the technological advancements, while laying the foundation for achieving the expected outcomes of the 6G-SANDBOX project.

KEYWORDS

Trial Networks, Platform, Facility, Final architecture, functional requirements, non-functional requirements, Trial network plane, user/control plane, experimentation plane, experimentation lifecycle, 6G-SANDBOX.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document builds upon the submission of deliverable D2.1, titled “Ecosystem Analysis and 6G-SANDBOX Facility Design” [1]. It is produced as part of WP2 “Ecosystem analysis and 6G-SANDBOX Facility design”, with a particular focus on Task 2.1 “6G-SANDBOX architecture and technologies”, aiming to describe the updated requirements for the 6G-SANDBOX Facility and the final complete framework design. In this context, the document advances the previous work by detailing the specific requirements for each architectural component and providing updates on this direction. Additionally, it presents a comprehensive and finalized architectural design and provides a high-level updated overview for each of the four platforms within the 6G-SANDBOX ecosystem. Compared to the previous deliverable, D2.1, the emphasis on the aforementioned points only, is aligned with the fact that dedicated deliverables addressing both Stakeholders (D2.3 Final definition of trial networks lifecycle) and KPIs (D2.4 Final release of KVI/KPI definition and validation methodology”) are scheduled for release in the coming months, M26 and M28 respectively

1.2 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The document is structured in 5 chapters. The current chapter includes introductory content about the deliverable. Chapter 2 presents the report of the functional and non-functional requirements elicited in the final stages of T2.1. Chapter 3 follows with the finalized version of the overall architecture. Chapter 4 presents the updated architecture of the four platforms including the extensions derived from the Open Calls (OCs) supported by the project. Finally, Chapter 5 presents the conclusions of this report.

1.3 TARGET AUDIENCE

The release of the deliverable is public, with the intent of exposing the final 6G-SANDBOX Facility to a wide variety of research individuals and communities. From specific to broader, the various target audiences for D2.2 are described below:

- The Project Consortium to validate that all objectives and proposed technological advancements have been fully analysed and to ensure that, through the identified and updated requirements (functional and non-functional), all the predefined actions have been completed. Furthermore, the deliverable sets to establish a common understanding among the Consortium with regards to i) the Facility architecture at its final format, and ii) the technologies that are utilised, deployed and extended per platform.
- The Research Community and funding agency (the European Commission -EC) to: i) summarise the 6G-SANDBOX scope, objectives and intended project innovations, ii) detail the final 6G-SANDBOX Facility and the four platforms as well as the targeted use cases that will be demonstrated and measure provided technological advancements, and iii) present the related requirements and associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that must be accomplished to achieve the expected results.
- Technology providers who are already engaged with the 6G-SANDBOX facility, as well as those who have expressed interest in contributing their own assets, and are now actively complementing the existing infrastructure, both through open calls and direct collaborations.

- Additionally, the general public, ensuring transparency and broader awareness of the technological progress made within the 6G-SANDBOX project.

2 6G-SANDBOX FACILITY REQUIREMENTS

2.1 APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

In the deliverable D2.1, a wide set of requirements were extracted and were analysed in depth by the consortium to formulate the initial 6G-SANDBOX Facility and guide the development process of the project. To move a step forward and shape the final design of the architecture, it was deemed mandatory to revisit that and provide a modernized version that prioritizes appropriately the initial list, while incorporating fundamental findings as the project work evolved.

The overall methodology outlined in D2.1 has been slightly updated, with the most effective approach being to categorize the requirements including the planes/clusters, that drive the new vision of the final architecture. More specifically the three pivotal planes in the perception of the project’s work are the User/Control, the Trial network, and the Experimentation. Thereafter, the requirements are classified and presented in two categories: functional and non-functional. Functional requirements correspond to the functionalities offered by the various components and non-functional reflect the quality properties that these software components need. Moreover, when applicable, the requirements are mapped to the relevant KPI stemming from the categorization of the main KPI families targeted by 6G-SANDBOX, as presented in D2.1. In detail, the revised template for describing the requirements is detailed in Table 1. The requirements are formulated around the expected capabilities constituting the 6G SANDBOX Facility, to be instantiated by the 6G SANDBOX platforms/testbeds.

Retrofitting the feedback from the project developments and the end-user requirements stemming from the Open Calls (OCs) OC1 and OC2 that the project has already supported, additional requirements (both functional and non-functional) have been identified and are presented as core updates following the new categorisation approach and format.

The goal has been to avoid an exhaustive and overly detailed list and focus on the most important factors to guide the final architecture design phase.

Table 1. Requirements Description template

Field	Title
REQ-ID	A unique ID, in the form of REQ-TYPE1-TYPE2-#,
Priority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory • Desirable • Optional
Description	A brief text explaining the requirement, including the objectives where necessary
Type	TYPE1=UC/TN/EXP/OC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UC: User/Control Plane

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TN: Trial Network Plane • EXP: Experimentation Plane • OC: Open call <p>TYPE2=F/NF</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • F: Functional • NF: Non-Functional
Release	<p>Release I: the initial architecture</p> <p>Release II: Final Architecture</p> <p>YES/NO (“Yes”: it was identified in the initial architecture/” No”: it was not identified in the initial architecture-it stands as new requirement in this release)</p>
KPI Mapping	The KPI as defined in D2.1 that the requirement is mapped with, where applicable

2.2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

2.2.1 USER-CONTROL PLANE

Table 2. User-Control plane functional requirements

REQ-UC-F-1	5G Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Coexistence
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Peak Data rate
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-1
Description	The Facility shall provide 5G RAN and core components to experiment, involving aggregation of technologies, standalone mode, and other interworking capabilities. Ensure seamless integration and coexistence of 5G RAN with core network components to support higher Download (DL) & Upload (UL) peak data rates.

REQ-UC-F-2	Modes of operation
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Data throughput, Spectral efficiency
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-2
Description	The 5G system (core network, RAN, and User Equipment (UE)) shall support standalone modes of operation to enable fully independent deployments, ensuring enhanced network efficiency, optimal performance, and scalability for diverse scenarios.

REQ-UC-F-3	Flexible Configuration of User Equipment
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	User data rate
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-3
Description	The Facility shall provide both commercial and experimental UEs with open Application Programmable Interfaces (APIs) to allow flexible configuration. Enable dynamic configuration of user equipment to achieve higher data rates.

REQ-UC-F-4	Utilisation of Edge nodes for experiments
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	U-Plane Latency
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-4
Description	The edge nodes of the Facility shall allow deployments that will support the use cases towards latency-sensitive applications.

REQ-UC-F-5	Integration of measurement probes and tools
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Reliability and Latency
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-5
Description	The Facility shall enable the deployment of measurement tools and probes. It shall also encompass the mechanisms for gathering relevant metrics required to validate the corresponding KPIs for the scenarios to be tested. Create tools that provide data for monitoring and optimization.

REQ-UC-F-6	Isolation of Resources
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Reliability and Security
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-6
Description	The Facility shall facilitate resource sharing and support multiple accesses (e.g. VPN, SSH, etc). Additionally, it will incorporate suitable mechanisms to ensure resource usage isolation and scheduling when necessary.

REQ-UC-F-7	Virtualised Computing environment
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Compute resources optimisation
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-7
Description	The Facility shall utilize virtualized computing infrastructure to enable function virtualization using virtual machines and/or containers. This approach will allow for computational resource optimization.

REQ-UC-F-8	Infrastructure as a Service
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Compute resources optimisation
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-8
Description	The deployed virtualized infrastructure shall provide interfaces and APIs that enable resource management and orchestration. This creates a scalable and flexible infrastructure able to facilitate various needs.

REQ-UC-F-9	Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) integration
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Area traffic capacity
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-9
Description	The underlying platforms shall encompass the integration of fixed/RAN and Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) with EDGE/Multi Access Edge Computing (MEC), and the utilization of satellite for mobile backhaul. It shall also include the emulation of satellite communication systems. This solution enhances coverage and reliability.

REQ-UC-F-10	Integration of different Access technologies
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Peak User data rate
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-10
Description	Access technologies, including fixed (mostly optical fiber), beyond 5G radio e.g., O-RAN and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS), shall be integrated. Enabling diverse connectivity options, allows for efficient spectrum utilisation and increased user data rate.

REQ-UC-F-11	Utilisation of the spectrum
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Spectral efficiency
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-11
Description	The platforms shall support beyond 5G spectrum. This should include licensed, unlicensed, or licensed-shared access. It also applies to the implementation of millimeter Wave (mmWave) technology to enhance spectrum use and achieve higher bandwidths.

REQ-UC-F-12	Regulations towards the use of the spectrum
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-INFRA FUNC-11
Description	Regulatory constraints with respect to 5G spectrum use must be abided.

2.2.2 TRIAL NETWORK PLANE

Table 3. Trial Network plane functional requirements

REQ-TN-F-1	Interaction with the Experimentation Layer
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Network capacity & Reliability
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 1
Description	The Trial network plane shall expose APIs for discoverability and secure access through the Common API framework (CAPIF), to its exposed functionalities. Such approach supports for innovation & testing.

REQ-TN-F-2	Component versioning for 6G Library compatibility
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The Trial Network Lifecycle Manager (TNLCM) must support versioning of each component in the 6G Library to allow updates and modifications without affecting other components, already-deployed Trial Networks, or the TNLCM itself.

REQ-TN-F-3	Deployment of Trial Network Components Using 6G Library Definitions
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The TNLCM must deploy each component of a Trial Network using the corresponding definitions from the 6G Library.

REQ-TN-F-4	Automating CAPIF Provider Onboarding
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The AEF (API Exposure Function) Gateway must handle the onboarding process of existing APIs by automating the CAPIF Provider onboarding operations.

REQ-TN-F-5	Enabling API Discoverability and Usability
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The AEF Gateway must publish the services into CAPIF, allowing for the APIs to be discoverable and usable through the CAPIF framework.

REQ-TN-F-6	REST API of Trial Network
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The Core component of the Trial Network must expose a REST API that other TNLCM components, platform owners, and experimenters can use for managing and inspecting Trial Networks.

REQ-TN-F-7	Trial Network Lifecycle Manager (TNLCM) Front End
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The TNLCM Front-End must provide a web interface tailored for platform owners to handle (pause, run, suspend, remove) all Trial Networks on the platform.

REQ-TN-F-8	Automated Trial Network Management
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Computational resources optimisation
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC- 4
Description	The system must support Schedulers (such as an Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELCM), OpenTap, Campaign Manager) that automatically retrieve the status of Trial Networks and perform changes to their status or configuration using the APIs provided by the Core component.

REQ-TN-F-9	Lifecycle Stages of Trial Network
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Computational resources optimisation
Release I	No
Description	Each Trial Network must be managed as a state machine, with states such as 'Running', 'Paused', etc., representing different stages of its lifecycle

REQ-TN-F-10	Provision of scalable networking tools
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	User density - Connection density
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 2
Description	Integration with digital twin platforms namely EXata shall be considered for network modelling and simulation to support scalable networking.

REQ-TN-F-11	Trial Network descriptor definition
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 3
Description	The Trial network plane shall provide a well-defined formalisation through the definition of a Trial Network Descriptor, including commands for the execution of actions such as the creation, modification, suspension, closure, and twinning of instances of the Trial Networks.

REQ-TN-F-12	Efficient translation of descriptors
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC- 4
Description	The TNLCM shall be able to receive TN Descriptor files regarding a specific TN implementation, and perform relevant actions to install, modify and deploy it.

REQ-TN-F-13	Isolation of resources
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Computational resources optimisation
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 5
Description	The TNLCM shall handle the management of the lifecycle of the Trial Network, from creation until decommission and the upkeep of their status, as well as the isolation of the different trial networks and the reserved resources.

REQ-TN-F-14	Flexibility towards the IaC
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 6
Description	The trial network plane shall support Infrastructure-as-code, including the creation of any required modifications, or the development of additional components that interface with IaaS provider to deliver additional functionalities. This approach enhances scalability and adaptability of the overall system under various needs and conditions.

REQ-TN-F-15	Utilisation of common Infrastructure Manager
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Computational resources optimisation
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 7
Release I	Yes
Description	A common Infrastructure manager shall be deployed for all the platforms. The infrastructure manager will allow maintenance of an up-to-date report of the usage of the resources. Such approach supports for resource optimization.

REQ-TN-F-16	RAN profiles
Priority	Desirable
KPI mapping	N/A
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 8
Release I	Yes
Description	The Trial Network plane shall expose a list of possible RAN configurations (either physical RAN or simulated) to be utilized by the experimenters. Such approach allows for radio access network configurations optimization and better utilization of components.

REQ-TN-F-17	Co-existence of trial networks
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Computational resource utilization/ optimization
D2.1 REQ	REQ-RM-FUNC 11
Release I	Yes
Description	Co-existence of multiple trial networks shall be allowed over the same infrastructure with the purpose to support diverse service requirements.

REQ-TN-F-1	Resource availability check and scheduling
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Computational resource utilization/ optimization
D2.1 REQ	N/A
Release I	No
Description	An experimentation scheduler shall allow the precise scheduling and reservation of equipment by checking the availability of resources at lower levels.

2.2.3 EXPERIMENTATION PLANE

Table 4. Experimentation plane functional requirements

REQ-EP-F-1	Support of modular extension through plugins
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-EXP-FUNC-2
Description	The manager as part of the Experimentation plane shall support the development, execution, and analysis of test plans by utilizing an architecture with plugins for any additional extensions. Such approach is enhancing the flexibility and scalability of the overall system.

REQ-EP-F-2	Dashboard for visualisation
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-EXP-FUNC-4
Description	The Experimentation plane shall provide visual representation of the experiment execution results through a graphical user interface, as well as automated reporting to the experimenter.

REQ-EP-F-3	Exposure of APIs to the experimenter
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-EXP-FUNC 1
Description	The Experimentation plane shall expose open APIs enabling the experimenter to access the Facility, define and conduct experiments as well as retrieve the results.

REQ-EP-F-4	KPIs collection within TN
Priority	Mandatory
Release I	No
Description	The Experimentation plane shall provide a repository for data gathering as well as processing of all experimental data to calculate and validate the target KPIs at the level of a TN

REQ-EP-F-4	Open repository at platform level
Priority	Mandatory
Release I	No
Description	The Experimentation plane shall support a repository at platform level for data gathering as well as processing of all experimental data to calculate and validate the target KPIs.

REQ-EP-F-5	Predefined baseline configurations and scenarios
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-EXP-FUNC 6
Description	The ELCM as part of the Experimentation plane, will provide experimenters with predefined baseline configurations and scenarios for component setup, which can be provisioned for experimentation.

REQ-EP-F-6	Creation of new testcases from the experimenters
Priority	Optional
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The Experimenters shall be able create their own test cases based on reference tasks included in the ELCM

REQ-EP-F-7	Software Development Kit (SDK) for integration with CAPIF
Priority	Optional
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The Experimentation plane shall provide an SDK to facilitate the creation of adapters (AEF) that helps the integration with OpenCAPIF [2]

REQ-EP-F-8	Generic API Exposure Function (AEF) provision
Priority	Optional
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	No
Description	The Experimentation plane shall offer a generic AEF functionality which will be configurable without coding to facilitate the overall process of exposing APIs

REQ-EP-F-9	Availability of tools and technologies per platform
Priority	Optional
KPI mapping	N/A
Release I	Yes
D2.1 REQ	REQ-EXP-FUNC 7
Description	As part of the Experimentation plane a set of components (6G Library components) will be provided to the experimenter via GUI to facilitate the creation of both simple and complex experiments.

2.3 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 5. 6G-SANDBOX Facility Non-functional requirements

REQ-NF-1	Status of Trial Network (TN)
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Operational Network Reliability
Release I	No
Description	The TNLCM must periodically check the status of registered Trial Networks at a defined interval without causing significant overhead or delays in operations

REQ-NF-1	User Friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI)
Priority	Mandatory
Release I	No
Description	The Front-End web applications must provide a user-friendly interface for platform owners, experimenters, or Trial Network owners, ensuring ease of use and efficient management of Trial Networks.

REQ-NF-1	Energy efficiency
Priority	Desirable
D2.1 REQ	REQ-NFUNC-10
Release I	Yes
Description	The Facility should prioritize and measure energy efficiency, aiming to monitor power consumption. Innovations in network hardware, algorithms, and power management techniques should be implemented to achieve sustainable and green network operations.

REQ-NF-1	AEF scaling capabilities
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Service safety, integrity, and maintainability
Release I	No
Description	The AEF Gateway must be capable of scaling to accommodate varying numbers of API integrations and Invoker requests

REQ-NF-1	AEF security
Priority	Mandatory
KPI mapping	Security Conformance
Release I	No
Description	The AEF Gateway must ensure secure handling of onboarding, publishing, and authorization processes

2.4 REQUIREMENTS FROM THIRD PARTIES ENGAGEMENT

The 6G-SANDBOX project supports the implementation of Open Calls (OCs) primarily aimed at enhancing the four platforms and subsequently the overall 6G-SANDBOX Facility. As part of this effort, the extensions developed during the OC2 phase are expected to evolve into components of the 6G

Library, further enriching the project's ecosystem. Given this context, the extraction of requirements from the OC1 and OC2 calls has been identified as a critical step to establish a solid foundation for shaping the final architecture. In this section, the functional and non-functional requirements of the *OC1 and OC2 extensions* are presented, providing clarity on the contributions needed to achieve the seamless integration of these extensions into the platforms.

OC1 and OC2 projects and their brief description are provided below in Table 6 and Table 7 respectively:

Table 6. OC1 projects' short description

OC1 extensions (projects)	Description of project
Astral project	Utilisation of popular open-source libraries (i.e., srsRAN) and to integrate them with the latest O-RAN near-RT RIC software.
Radiant project	Custom made Release (Rel)-16 5G modems
Analysat project	Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) capability; Location information capability; Multilink backhaul management in hybrid terrestrial-satellite networks.
Arrow project	AI-enabled SDN system offering a complete experimental environment for cybersecurity for 5G and beyond ecosystems
6GLoRAGRAN project	Integration of Long-Range Wireless Access Network (LoRaWAN) network in the 6G SANDBOX facility (selected platforms)
ONEmNEF project	Integration Microservice-based NEF into the 6G-SANDBOX facility
RAYPLICATE project	Creation of a realistic and specific PHY-layer in the digital twin used in 6G-SANDBOX (EXata) via a ray-tracing that replicates the radio channel properties

Table 7. OC2 projects' description

OC2 extensions (projects)	Description of project
REACT-6G project	Utilisation of Radio Units (RUs), UEs, transport network and time/frequency synchronisation to deliver a 5G Stand-Alone Non-Public Network (SNPN), aligned to Open RAN.
NWDAF_StreamAnalyzer project	Cloud native streaming analytics platform, (including a wide set of machine learning and AI methods and frameworks for generation of statistics and predictions over large volumes of streaming data) towards the implementation of NWDAF APIs.
RISFORCE project	Deployment of mmWave FR2 (n257) RIS to provide a more reliable and efficient wireless connectivity, either on coverage enhancement or performance improvement in the outdoor environment.

2.4.1 OC1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 8. OC1 functional requirements

REQ-OC1-F-1	Container based deployment
Name of the project	ONEmNEF
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The system shall be deployed on a container orchestration platform.
REQ-OC1-F-2	UE connection for NEF Testing
Name of the project	ONEmNEF
Priority	Mandatory
Description	At least one UE must be connected for functional testing and validation of Network Exposure Function (NEF) functionalities.
REQ-OC1-F-3	Core Network Operation for NEF Support
Name of the project	ONEmNEF
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The core network must be fully operational to support the proper functioning of NEF functionalities

REQ-OC1-F-4	Machine Learning Framework Integration
Name of the project	ONEmNEF
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must integrate a machine learning framework to support functionalities such as traffic classification

REQ-OC1-F-5	Radio parameters retrieval for LMF configuration
Name of the project	ANALYSAT
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must enable the retrieval of key radio parameters through REST API or websocket API, required for network performance assessment and the configuration of the LMF (Location Management Function).

REQ-OC1-F-6	NTN Support for Multilink Backhaul and Traffic Steering
Name of the project	ANALYSAT
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility shall support NTN capabilities for the multilink backhaul management implementation and traffic steering

REQ-OC1-F-7	Resource provision and VM deployment
Name of the project	ANALYSAT
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must provide the necessary resources to host the implementations, including the deployment of virtual machines (VMs)

REQ-OC1-F-8	SDN Controller Deployment for Network Management
Name of the project	ARROW
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must support the deployment a Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller for real-time monitoring and control over the network elements within the platform, allowing centralized network management and security policy enforcement.

REQ-OC1-F-9	Access for Security Testing in 5G Core Testbed
Name of the project	ARROW
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must provide access to key areas of the 5G core testbed, specifically targeting points that are vulnerable to attacks, to facilitate security testing.

REQ-OC1-F-10	RAN Connectivity for 5G Core Traffic Simulation
Name of the project	ARROW
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The testbed must be connected to a RAN deployment capable of generating typical 5G core traffic to simulate realistic use-case scenarios.

REQ-OC1-F-11	Container Orchestration Platform Deployment
Name of the project	ARROW
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must support the deployment of a container orchestration platform to ensure efficient management, scaling, and deployment of containerized applications.

REQ-OC1-F-12	Support for performance evaluation tools
Name of the project	ARROW
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must support specific measurement tools and equipment (e.g. CYPREF) for evaluating the ARROW platform's performance.

REQ-OC1-F-13	Kubernetes GPU Cluster for AI Processing
Name of the project	ASTRAL
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must include a Kubernetes Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) cluster to support Artificial Intelligence (AI) processing tasks efficiently.

REQ-OC1-F-14	Support of SDR Radio Equipment
Name of the project	ASTRAL
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must provide Software-Defined Radio (SDR) equipment, such as Ettus Research models, for testing and experimentation

REQ-OC1-F-15	Integration of ray tracing with channel emulator
Name of the project	RAYPLICATE
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must integrate a ray-tracing solution with Keysight's channel emulator for advanced channel modelling and simulation

REQ-OC1-F-17	Integration of ray tracing with network modelling simulator
Name of the project	RAYPLICATE
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must integrate a ray-tracing solution with Keysight's EXata Network Modelling for enhanced network performance simulation and analysis

REQ-OC1-F-84	Remote Experimentation Support
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must enable researchers to conduct remote experimental campaigns with control over traffic patterns, slices, channels, and spreading factors.

REQ-OC1-F-19	Compatibility with Multiple 5GCs
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must ensure integration approaches that are compatible with multiple 5GC platforms, including Amarisoft 5G and Open5GS, potentially without the need for non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF).

REQ-OC1-F-20	Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF)
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Optional
Description	The Platforms 5G Core shall support the N3IWF function to incorporate LoRaWAN into the 5G core of 6G-SANDBOX sites.

REQ-OC1-F-21	Network Slicing for LoRaWAN
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Optional
Description	Implement a network slicing solution in the LoRaWAN radio access network, allocating specific radio resources for motes based on their assigned slices.

2.4.2 OC1 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 9. OC1 Non-functional requirements

REQ-OC1-NF-1	Role and Role Binding Management
Name of the project	ONEmNEF
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The system must support the creation of roles and role bindings, ensuring proper security practices are followed to manage access and permissions effectively

REQ-OC1-NF-2	Scalability of the testbed for future expansions
Name of the project	ANALYSAT
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must be capable of accommodating future expansion and the addition of new network components without degradation of performance

REQ-OC1-NF-3	Data Protection and Privacy Compliance
Name of the project	ARROW
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must ensure that all operations, including data handling and processing, comply with relevant data protection regulations such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), maintaining user data privacy and implementing appropriate security measures to protect sensitive information

REQ-OC1-NF-4	High Accuracy Prediction of Radio Channel Properties
Name of the project	RAYPLICATE
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must achieve high accuracy in predicting radio channel properties with a root mean square error (RMSE) for received power (within the range of 5-8 dB)

REQ-OC1-NF-5	Adaptability
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Optional
Description	The Facility should be easily adaptable to future expansions or changes in network infrastructure and technology advancements

REQ-OC1-NF-6	Efficiency
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must optimize resource block allocation in the LoRaWAN network to ensure efficient use of radio resources and maintain data rate and coverage.

REQ-OC1-NF-7	Reliability
Name of the project	6G-LoRaGRAN
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must ensure consistent performance and reliable data transmission for both loose and tight integration scenarios.

2.4.3 OC2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 10. OC2 functional requirements

REQ-OC2-F-1	Access to network metrics
Name of the project	NWDAF Stream_Analyzer
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must provide access to necessary network metrics from sources such as Amarisoft's Web Socket API and Open5GS metrics exposed via Prometheus
REQ-OC2-F-2	Real time data streaming capabilities
Name of the project	NWDAF Stream_Analyzer
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must ensure stable and high-throughput data streams from Amarisoft and Open5GS from the testbed to the analytics' platform
REQ-OC2-F-3	Resource Management by VIM
Name of the project	FLOW QOS 6G
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The facility must utilize a Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM), such as Kubernetes, to manage the resourcing and execution of each Pod.
REQ-OC2-F-4	Containerization of Core Network Services
Name of the project	FLOW QOS 6G
Priority	Mandatory
Description	Each Core Network (CN) service must be packaged into containers, organized into Pods, to facilitate cloud-native orchestration.
REQ-OC2-F-5	Quality of Service (QoS) Enforcement and Traffic Observation
Name of the project	FLOW QOS 6G
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The platform must integrate In-kernel flow monitoring (MantisNet) and model-based supervised learning (WAN-AI) for observing network traffic and optimizing bandwidth resource utilization.
REQ-OC2-F-6	QoS Flow Mapping
Name of the project	FLOW QOS 6G
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility must map several QoS flows directly to user applications, ensuring that specific applications like YouTube streams are assigned to single 5G QoS flows.

2.4.4 OC2 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 11. OC2 Non-functional requirements

REQ-OC2-NF-1	Availability of devices
Name of the project	NWDAF Stream_Analyzer
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The testbed must ensure the availability of devices that can connect to the testbed and consistently produce traffic for data capture. This availability includes both physical devices and simulated UEs
REQ-OC2-NF-2	Resource Efficiency
Name of the project	FLOW QOS 6G
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The orchestration must minimize the number of UPF Pods running to reduce operational costs while maintaining required QoS levels.
REQ-OC2-NF-3	Interoperability
Name of the project	FLOW QOS 6G
Priority	Mandatory
Description	The Facility should integrate seamlessly with existing ETSI MANO frameworks, Kubernetes, and other network components such as Cumucore 5GC and Platform Open5GS.

3 6G-SANDBOX FACILITY

3.1 DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The initial architecture of the 6G-SANDBOX project, described in D2.1, adopted a layered approach, consisting of the Infrastructure, Resource, and Experimentation layers. However, as the project evolved, the architectural focus shifted towards a more modular design, by developing a flexible architecture, where components are designed as independent, self-contained modules. These modules communicate seamlessly through well-defined, standardized APIs, ensuring smooth interaction while maintaining their autonomy. In the initial architecture special emphasis has been placed on five key characteristics that improve the long-term support and continuous evolution of the 6G-SANDBOX facility. The same principles have been taken into consideration, nonetheless, updated to reflect the progress of the project's developments. The updated approach is graphically depicted in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Overall Project Approach and design methodology

The overarching guiding principles are:

- **Modularity**, in composing both the 6G-SANDBOX Facility architecture and Trial Network Design as independent, self-contained components, ensuring standardised, well-defined APIs and means of interworking.
- **Openness**, in the context of exposure is endorsed and promoted through the use of 3GPP CAPIF, which serves as the foundation for the 6G-SANDBOX API Framework and facilitates the exposure of extensions from the OCs by ensuring access to the different functionalities through unified and standardized interfaces. In the context of sourcing practise, the software components developed within the project, as well as those originating from the OCs, are released as open-source whenever possible and are included in the 6G Library, promoting the collaboration of the community in a broader scope.

- **Reusability** stems from the Consortium's commitment to openness and is further supported by the creation of reusable patterns, such as Trial Network templates. These templates facilitate pre-defined use cases and provide a solid foundation for the scope of reusability. The Trial Network concept also distinguishes actual experimentation from the configuration of underlying resources, allowing the same Trial Network to be effortlessly instantiated on different experimentation platforms. This flexibility extends to scenarios where physical components are unavailable, by integrating the Digital Twin concept via EXata software, as part of the 6G Library.
- **Innovation** is driven by the definition of the Trial Network, which aims to simplify experimentation and trial management while enabling platforms to adopt a zero-touch management approach. The updated approach of the architecture not only reinforces modularity but also makes it easier to incorporate innovative technologies into the 6G-SANDBOX platforms over time.
- **Sustainability** is achieved by prioritizing robust support for emerging 6G experimentation needs. The final architecture has been designed with tangible inputs from experimenters participating in OCs, future engagement with SNS JU projects, as well as additional external experimenters.

Following the layering approach for addressing the 6G SANDBOX architecture, mapping of the layers & modules foreseen with the realisation of the project's ambitions has been performed also depicted in Figure 1. In this way it is ensured that all project ambitions are appropriately incorporated in the target architecture. The ambitions set refer to:

- Amb#1: Ambition in Experimentation Processes and Facilities
- Amb#2: Ambition in Disruptive wireless
- Amb#3: Ambition in fixed/RAN/NTN integration
- Amb#4: Ambition in Deterministic networking enablers
- Amb#5: Ambition in Interaction with Network Core
- Amb#6: Ambition in AI/ML network evolution
- Amb#7: Ambition in Security as a Service
- Amb#8: Ambition in Edge-cloud continuum
- Amb#9: Ambition in Digital twins
- Amb#10: Ambition in Extended Reality (XR)-Haptics

3.2 FINAL ARCHITECTURE

Starting from the basic design principles as outlined above, the new modular approach of the architecture is structured around three primary planes. The **User/Control Plane**, the **Experimentation Plane**, and the **Trial Network Plane**, each serving a distinct purpose within the architecture. In a nutshell, the **User/Control Plane** focuses on managing the interactions, connections, and data transmission within a trial network. Moreover, it ensures seamless operation, and effective communication among network components and the elements of the platforms. The **Experimentation Plane** is dedicated to facilitating the design, execution, and monitoring of experiments. Finally, the **Trial Network Plane** handles the deployment and configuration of trial networks, separating the physical and virtual resources from the experimental setups. Together, these planes form an integrated framework, as illustrated in Figure 2 below, enabling a modular and efficient

architecture tailored to the needs of 6G experiments and the main objective of 6G-SANDBOX to provide tangible contribution towards an experimentation ecosystem for 6G in Europe.

Figure 2. Final Architecture of 6G-SANDBOX Facility

3.2.1 USER/CONTROL PLANE

The User/Control Plane (Blue line in Figure 2) is responsible for managing the components of a trial network, orchestrating their interactions, and configuring key functions such as routing and connection control to ensure that the trial network operates effectively. At the same time, it ensures routing and connectivity through the route manager, facilitating integration with diverse physical resources included in the four platforms of 6G-SANDBOX. These resources encompass compute infrastructure, outdoor and Open-Radio Access Network (O-RAN), Next Generation NodeB (gNBs), Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), and other experimental physical tools that the platforms offer.

3.2.2 TRIAL NETWORK PLANE

The Trial Network Plane (Brown line in Figure 2) plays a pivotal role in the 6G-SANDBOX platform, managing the interactions between the TNLCM, the 6G Library, and the Infrastructure Manager. The foundational step for the interaction among the modules, involves enriching the 6G Library with software components [3] and representation models of the physical components located at the four 6G-SANDBOX platforms. During this phase, the TNLCM acquires awareness of the platform capabilities and resource availability for each 6G-SANDBOX platform. A trial network user (experimenter) utilises the TN portal to establish a TN (TN setup). Once the experimenter defines the TN by creating a descriptor that outlines the required components and their configurations through the Facility's portal, this descriptor is sent to the TNLCM for further processing. The TNLCM ensures that all necessary information is available for setting up the trial network and prepares for its deployment, verifying that all components are properly configured. When the TN is ready for deployment, the TNLCM initiates the deployment process, coordinating with automation tools to carry out the necessary tasks via the TN scheduler. The role of the scheduler is managing a set of TNs in the system,

allowing also temporal suspension of TNs, with the intention to conserve resources when experimenters are using the TN sporadically to run several experimental campaigns.

For the virtual infrastructure components of the trial network, OpenNebula is selected as the common Infrastructure Manager for all the platforms. Its responsibility is to manage the underlying infrastructure, including optionally deploying a Kubernetes cluster, or virtual machines on an already running system. OpenNebula ensures that the trial network components are provisioned and configured according to the experimenter's specifications and based on the availability of resources across the platforms.

3.2.3 EXPERIMENTATION PLANE

The Experimentation Plane (Green line in Figure 2) focuses on executing and managing the experiments within the trial networks. The key component is the Experiment Lifecycle Manager that orchestrates the lifecycle of an experiment. With the aim to create meaningful and long-term impact, the 6G KPIs and Key Value Indicators (KVI) measured during the experiment will be made available to any interested party. A repository for storing KPIs stemming from the experiments on top of a TN is also interconnected through this plane. Additionally, the developments and APIs generated will populate an open repository, serving as a first step toward extending the project's contributions and insights beyond its boundaries. This repository is represented in Figure 2 as the 6G KPI and KVI open repository. The plan is to use this repository as the anchor for relevant initiatives (e.g., Slices, Test Measurement Validation Working Group (TMV WG), Data spaces etc.). More details for the latter will be provided as part of T2.3 in the D2.4 "Final release of KVI/KPI definition and validation methodology" due in M28 (April 2025).

Each platform has OpenTap Runner(s)-there can be multiple runners in a platform, each in different trial networks deployed-which is responsible for the execution of test plans and running tests on the local instrumentation. This Runner is connected to two central cloud locations. The first of these is the OpenTap package repository. To interface with any instrument, tool or outside device, the OpenTap runner needs to have a bespoke plugin designed to enable communication and control. These plugins, when published, are stored on the OpenTap Package Repository and therefore the runner needs access to this repo to fetch the necessary plugins for a given operation. This only needs to be done once, meaning necessary plugins can be pre-loaded. However, a consistent connection must be maintained to allow the runner to check for and download any required updates for installed plugins. The other external cloud resource that the Runner needs access to, is the KS8500 Cloud Automation environment [4], specifically the 6G-SANDBOX Realm. From this location, test plans and campaigns can be pushed to the runner for execution. The progress of said tests can be monitored, and any generated results/artefacts can be downloaded from this location as well.

Figure 3. Abstract representation of the experimentation approach on Trial Network

As previously mentioned, the TNLCM serves as the central intelligence behind the realization of the Trial Network Concept. Trial Networks are realised by the experimenters as complete end to end testbeds which are based on the utilisation of the available components and their descriptions hosted in a library (6G-library) [5] and managed primarily by the TNLCM. Within the 6G-SANDBOX architecture, the TNLCM ensures that each Trial Network across all platforms remains accessible and fully operational, while orchestrating the actions needed to manage and modify the state of a Trial Network as required. Building on this premise, Figure 3 above, illustrates an abstract representation of the experimentation approach with Trial Networks and how a Trial Network User (TNU) interacts with the 6G-SANDBOX Facility. More details about the third-party roles and the experimentation potential, can be found in the Whitepaper [6] that the project has published. Additionally in the upcoming deliverable D2.3 (due at M26 -February 2025) within the scope of T2.2, a stakeholder analysis will be presented.

In the light of the above, the experimentation process initiated by a TNU can be clearly defined in 4 main steps:

1. Platform capability awareness (Step 1)
2. Trial Network Setup via Front-End Portal (Step 2)
3. Experimentation Manager Selection and Execution (Step 3)
4. Trial Network Management and Resource Scheduling (Step 4).

The experimentation process as described above, can be facilitated by the 6G-SANDBOX Toolkit [6], which serves as a comprehensive software solution for operators of 5G/6G platforms to enable the creation and management of Trial Networks. Leveraging components from the 6GLibrary, the Toolkit automates resource allocation and exposure, supporting advanced capabilities such as platform sharing for concurrent testbeds.

4 6G-SANDBOX PLATFORMS

Given that 6G-SANDBOX facility is built on top of individual platforms, this section focuses on detailing the architecture of the four platforms (Athens, Berlin, Malaga, Oulu) and the updates that have taken place as part of the overall architecture's final iteration. By highlighting the functionality expansions, component upgrades, and incorporation of new technologies, this section provides a comprehensive overview of the advancements made to elevate platform performance, adaptability, and to augment the concept of the TN. The purpose is to highlight only the key features and updates across the four platforms as part of the architecture's final iteration and not delve into technical details. Detailed descriptions of the integration activities, technical enhancements, and component upgrades will be provided in the WP4 deliverable. For all platforms the updates stemming from OC1 are highlighted in a red frame, while the extensions coming from OC2 are highlighted in blue

4.1 ATHENS PLATFORM FINAL ARCHITECTURE

While the core architecture of the 6G-SANDBOX Athens platform remains the same, the focus is now shifted on the extensions and additional functionalities incorporated to enhance its capabilities and abide to the 6G-SANDBOX requirements. In particular, these efforts include the various upgrades and infrastructure replacements to support state-of-the-art technologies introduced by the project. Noteworthy architectural expansions for the Athens platform include:

- Design of a single cloud infrastructure spanning seamlessly across both Athens platform's sites (NCSRD, OTE), completely abstracting, and sharing the respective infrastructure resources under one single administrative domain yet managing two separate and diverse (in terms of resources and characteristics) infrastructure domains. This has been designed following OpenNebula's networking principles, conforming to the 6G-SANDBOX best practices.
- Design of a single TNLCM being capable, through the unified VIM to manage TNs with components spanning in both sites.
- Parameterisation of a mmWave gNB for interworking with RIS components developed by the project
- Support the Multi-Operator Mobile Core Network (MOCN) operation among the test mobile networks provided by NCSRD and COSMOTE.

Additionally, extensions provided by the OC1 and OC2 activities have been seamlessly incorporated, further elevating the platform's overall performance and adaptability.

More specifically from OC1 the Athens platform has been enhanced with the following aspects:

- The Multi-Link Backhaul Management functionality (MLBM) that abstracts transport segment management, enabling user plane traffic steering between terrestrial or satellite paths on a per-network slice basis.
- The Location Management Function (LMF)
- The NWDAF-core component through modified and custom-made approach on top of Free5gc Core network [7]
- The microservice-based NEF provides NEF APIs, which encompass Traffic Influence and QoS through the AsSessionWithQoS functionality.

As far as OC2 is concerned, the enhancement focuses on the implementation of Stream_Analyzer, a streaming analytics platform which has the functionality to derive statistics and predictions over large volumes of streaming data coming from the network (both from Amarisoft 5G all in one and Open5GS with Amarisoft RAN). Based on these data, specific NDWF functionalities of the 3GPP NWDAF APIs are built (e.g., Events Subscription, Analytics Info, Data Management & ML Model Provision) and are tested through dedicated use cases, to validate the proper functionality of NWDAF approach. The overall updated architecture of Athens platform is illustrated in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Updated Architecture of Berlin platform

4.2 BERLIN PLATFORM FINAL ARCHITECTURE

The fundamental architecture of the 6G-SANDBOX Berlin platform has been preserved, with enhancements and additional functionalities integrated to bolster its capabilities. Notably, these enhancements have concentrated on a variety of improvements aimed at augmenting the platform's functionalities, such as expanding existing capabilities, performing upgrades, and replacing components to accommodate the cutting-edge technologies introduced by the project (TNLCM and 6G-SANDBOX Toolkit integration).

Moreover, extensions from the OC1 and OC2 activities have been integrated as they became available, significantly enhancing the platform's overall performance and adaptability. In the accompanying platform diagram, extensions from OC1 are highlighted in red, while those from OC2 are depicted in blue. The Berlin platform was extended during the OC1 activities as part of the 6G-LoraGran project, which established an interconnection with the LoRaWAN testbed at the University of Granada. Additionally, within the RADIANT OC1 Project, plans were made to enhance the platform with 3GPP Release 16 5G devices provided by Fivecomm. However, this enhancement was rescheduled to the OC2 timeframe. Looking ahead, the FLOW QoS 6G OC2 Project aims to integrate its final solution after the conclusion of the OC2 implementation phase in early 2025. This project focuses on automating QoS configuration in the User Plane Function (UPF) to enable more efficient and dynamic network slicing. The overall revised architecture of the Berlin platform is shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Updated Architecture of Berlin platform

4.3 MALAGA PLATFORM FINAL ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the 6G-SANDBOX Málaga platform continues to center around its main location in the Ada Byron building (located on the University of Málaga campus), where the core infrastructure is housed. This facility serves as the central hub for managing and controlling the RAN deployments across all locations. The Ada Byron site itself has been significantly enhanced with additional RAN equipment, including both fixed and portable solutions of traditional and O-RAN:

- New portable solutions include NOKIA SA for FR2 bands and Amarisoft SA for FR1 bands.
- A new fixed solution is also coming from Vicinity small cell.
- New O-RAN solutions are provided by IS-Wireless and LiteOn.

Additionally, new 5G/B5G networks have been deployed at the following sites to provide coverage and support various specialized activities:

- La Mayora, enabling 5G/B5G connectivity to support agriculture-focused research and testing activities.
- Malaga TechPark, delivering 5G/B5G coverage tailored for connected car technologies and vehicular communication experiments.

Further enhancements implemented during the OC1 and OC2 phases are highlighted in Figure 6, where extensions from OC1 are marked in red, and those from OC2 are marked in blue.

During the OC1 phase, the Malaga platform saw substantial growth through the integration of the following extensions:

- ASTRAL, which provided an O-RAN solution by integrating srsRAN with its own E2 agent to allow connectivity with RIC, for xApps development.

- ARROW, which implemented a cybersecurity framework to enhance the platform's robustness.
- ONEmNEF, providing a robust integration of a NEF (Network Exposure Function) to facilitate service exposure.
- RAYPLICATE, which introduced an enhanced network digital twin leveraging raytracing technologies.
- RADIANT, which supplied 3GPP Release 16 devices, contributing to the platform's UE pool.

Looking into the OC2 phase, the Malaga platform anticipates a major new extension, developed as part of the consortium-led REACT-6G project. This includes:

- Integration of srsRAN Distributed Unit (DU) with Accelleran dRAX, incorporating both the Centralized Unit (CU) and Non-RT/ Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs)
- On top of this, the development of new xApps is underway, focusing on energy efficiency improvements and enhanced handover mechanisms to optimize network performance.

Furthermore, an NTN gateway will be installed at the University of Málaga campus during 2025, enabling a collaboration with the European Space Agency (ESA).

Figure 6. Updated Architecture of Malaga platform

4.4 OULU PLATFORM FINAL ARCHITECTURE

The core structure of the 6G-SANDBOX Oulu platform has been maintained including several key developments towards 5G-SA capability, O-RAN integration, transport network upgrades, Rel. 16 and 17 features, new frequency bands, and 6G technology enablers. The new network architecture is illustrated in Figure 7 and detailed below.

5G-SA Capability: Four standalone cores—Nokia SA-core, Open5GS, Allbesmart, and Cumucore—have been deployed, enabling distinct overlay networks for various projects and purposes. O-RAN network was introduced with FlexRIC and it is supporting experiments with end-to-end slicing, demonstrated through concurrent eMBB and uRLLC slices. Functional split between the DU and RU has been

introduced with two different splits: 7.2a and 8. Devices used for the Split 8 are USRP models N310 and X410 in FR1 and Benetel for the 7.2a. Integration of FR2 LiteOn RU is on-going and it will be introduced during the 1Q/2025. The transport network has been upgraded to 100 Gbit/s-capable routers, new switches, advanced computing servers, and FortiGate firewall hardware and software. This overhaul centralized all baseband processing into a baseband hotel, eliminated bottlenecks, and enhanced transport capacity and connectivity. RAN supports new base stations with Rel. 16 and some Rel. 17 features, improving latency and expanding network services. All the radios have been renewed in the n77, n78 and n258 bands, are featuring 36 new indoor radio heads, three new macro base stations for n77, three new macro base stations for n78 and a new indoor base station for n258 (mmWave). TSN (Time Sensitive Networking) is being developed for both wired LAN and WiFi environments.

In terms of 6G enablers, in-house RIS platform prototypes were developed, with commercial RIS solutions being integrated from two manufacturers. Progress includes 140 GHz transceiver development, and a "network-on-wheels" van equipped with base stations, power amplifiers, LNAs, an SA core, multichannel routers, and backhaul via 5G networks and Starlink for remote connectivity.

The Oulu platform, during the OC1 execution, was equipped with 5G modems (Rel. 16) to connect various user devices (e.g., cameras, drones) aiming to meet diverse requirements and scenarios stemming from industrial verticals. On the Oulu platform for the OC2 and OC3 rounds, the focus is exclusively on experimentations.

Figure 7. Updated Architecture of Oulu platform

In OC2, no extension is being hosted; instead, a series of experiments are being conducted. The decision not to host an implementation is due to the outcomes of the open calls, specifically the nature of submissions—where proposers expressed interest in particular facilities—and the subsequent evaluations, where independent experts selected the implementations.

4.5 SUMMARY OF PLATFORMS FEATURES

This section provides an overview of the technologies and extensions contributed by the Open Calls (OCs) across the four testbeds. It consolidates the deployments drawn from the project's detailed timeline towards OCs, offering a clear and comprehensive understanding of the current capabilities of the platforms after the extensions. Additionally, it highlights the progress and status of developments aimed at enhancing the platforms to better support the experimental activities facilitated by the project during OC1 and OC2 rounds. In order to signify the deployments that were supported during OC1 a checkmark symbol ('✓') is used, while the technologies stemming from OC2 are represented by the symbol ('o'). Moreover, the table below highlights the distribution and replication of the technological solutions across the four platforms.

Table 12. Summary of all OC extensions in four platforms

Technology/enabler	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
Multi-Link Backhaul Management functionality (MLBM)	✓			
Location Management Function (LMF)	✓			
Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF)	✓			
NEF APIs Traffic Influence, AsSessionWithQoS	✓	✓	✓	
LoRaWAN		✓	✓	
3GPP Release 16 5G modems	✓	✓	✓	✓
O-RAN solution by integrating srsRAN with an own E2 agent to allow connectivity with RIC			✓	
AI-enabled SDN system for infrastructure monitoring			✓	

Digital Twin simulation with ray tracing			✓	
User Plane Function (UPF) dynamic network slicing		o		
Streaming analytics platform providing Events Subscription, Analytics Info, Data Management & ML Model Provision NWDAF APIs	o			
srsRAN with Non-RT/ Near-RT RICs			o	

5 CONCLUSION

This document presents the final update of Deliverable D2.1, "Ecosystem Analysis and 6G-SANDBOX Facility Design," and outlines the results and activities of T2.1, "6G-SANDBOX Architecture and Technologies" which ends with the submission of this document.

Initially, the deliverable captures the key outcomes of the collaborative process for gathering, harmonizing, and updating the initial requirements, which have shaped the final and updated architecture of the 6G-SANDBOX Facility. This updated architecture is presented in detail, focusing on the three distinct planes that define the project's goal of providing clear and tangible contributions to a 6G experimentation ecosystem in Europe. Additionally, the document explores each individual platform in detail, in parallel with the finalization of the architecture, highlighting their updated topology and technological enhancements resulting from the OCs engagement process

In summary, this document serves as a comprehensive guide for external stakeholders to clearly understand the concept and objectives of the project. It provides an accessible overview, making it an effective resource for individuals and organizations to quickly grasp the project's vision by outlining the architectural approach in a structured manner.

6 REFERENCES

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ANNEX 1

Updated Glossary

Term	Description
Facility (or the 6G-SANDBOX facility) (or 6G-Experimentation facility)	The full set of 6G-SANDBOX components that are offered as a pan-European testbed for experimenting. The testing procedures can be for 6G technology validations and for 6G KPI measurements. The facility is expected to include the implementation of all the components that will be structured around a 6G-SANDBOX reference architecture.
Experimentation platform (or Platform)	An End-to-End platform (a system with integrated Radio Access Network, Network Core, Transport and services) that include 6G-enabled components/features and experimentation services as well as local cloud infrastructure capabilities. Four platforms support the 6G-SANDBOX project, namely the Malaga platform, the Athens Platform, the Berlin platform, and the Oulu platform.
Site (or Platform's Site) (or Experimentation platform's Site)	A location-dependent part of an experimentation platform. The various sites of a platform should be well interconnected and interfaced, but this interconnection and interfacing is not necessarily exposed to platform externals. Example: the Athens platform of 6G-SANDBOX is composed of parts that are located in the COSMOTE premises (i.e., parts that define the COSMOTE site of the platform, e.g., the 5G core) and parts at the NCSR campus (i.e., parts that define the NCSR site of the platform, e.g., the 5G access); these two sites are well-connected with an optical fiber link.
Node	It refers to every physical or virtual component that can be identified individually, i.e., it has specific purpose (provides a kind of service) and it encompass one or multiple technological features. Examples are a 5G-NR antenna, a RIS system, an IoT end-device, a network application, a network function, a set of network functions that compose network core, an experimentation tool, etc.
Trial Network	Fully configurable, manageable and controllable network which combines digital/virtual and physical nodes and provides services for 6G technology validation and 6G KPI measurements. Instances of Trial Networks might be offered targeting specific network domains and technologies. End-to-end Trial Networks will be offered by the four experimentation platforms that support the 6G-SANDBOX project.
6G Library	To support reusability, openness, and long-term evolution a meaningful set of software components -that will be provided to and/or developed for the 6G-SANDBOX facility - will be packed and offered in a relevant repository (e.g., GitHub) together with the required documentation in order to create an open reference software library, which will not only be under continuous enhancement by the

	project partners, but it is also meant to serve as an index and sink point for other developments (during and beyond the project lifetime).
6G KPI and KVI repository	To maximize the contribution towards a 6G experimentation ecosystem, all the results of the experimentation processes performed on the 6G-SANDBOX facility will be stored in an open 6G KPI & KVI repository following a common and structured format (based on the SNS JU work in the related WGs) and they will be accessible by other projects/stakeholders, and thus, subject to external analysis.
Technology validation test (or 6G Technology validation)	Tests using the 6G-SANDBOX facility targeting to assess whether a component/node operates and interacts properly and also provide expected results. The Technology validation tests target the assessment of components/nodes within an overall system. E.g., the tests to validate that the API framework of 6G-SANDBOX is well integrated in the overall testbed.
Final Architecture	The main representation of the 6G-SANDBOX facility and the interactions among its components.
User/Control plane	The plane introduced in the updated architecture, focusing on the interactions, connections, and data transmission within a trial network, ensuring smooth operation and efficient communication between network components and platform elements.
Trial Network plane	The Trial Network Plane within the updated architecture handles the deployment and configuration of trial networks, separating the physical and virtual resources from the experimental setups
Experimentation plane	The Experimentation Plane is dedicated to facilitating the design, execution, and monitoring of experiments.
Everything as a code	It refers to the philosophy behind the design of each 6G Library component, as self-contained units equipped with the necessary automations and scripts for deployment within a 6G-SANDBOX platform.
6G-SANDBOX Trial Network User (TNU)	Someone that creates test cases (or uses the available ones) and conducts measurement campaigns. The TNU can also bring an application, deploy it, and link it (through API interaction) to a Trial Network that is selected and activated for the experiment.
6G-SANDBOX Trial Network Operator/Owner (TNO)	Someone that creates a Trial Network from the components that the 6G-SANDBOX facility provides (i.e., the 6G-Library and the technologies physically integrated in the 6G-SANDBOX Platforms). The TNO can also play the role of a TNU or allow other TNUs to conduct experiment to the Trial Network created.
Third party Technology Provider for the 6G-SANDBOX facility	Someone that brings 6G component(s) or software solutions and is willing to integrate them with one or more Platforms for expanding the 6G-SANDBOX capabilities.

Third party host for the 6G SANDBOX framework	An owner of an end-to end experimentation platform / testbed who is interested in adopting 6G-SANDBOX framework (i.e., the concept of creating TNs on top of the testbed)
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ANNEX 2

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programmable Interface
AEF	API Exposure Function
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CU	Central Unit
DL	Downlink
DU	Distributed Unit
EC	European Commission
ELCM	Experiment Lifecycle Manager
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
gNB	Next Generation Node B
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
KPI	Key performance indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LMF	Location Management Function
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wireless Access Network
mmWave	Millimeter Wave
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi Access Edge Computing
MLBM	Multi-Link Backhaul Management
MOCN	Multi-Operator Core Network
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
N3IWF	non-3GPP Interworking Function
NTN	Non-Terrestrial Networks

NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OC	Open Call
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RU	Radio Unit
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SNPN	Standalone Non-Public Network
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
TN	Trial Network Descriptor
TND	Trial Network Descriptor
TNLCM	Trial Network Lifecycle Manager
TNU	Trial Network User
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
WAN	Wireless Access Network

6G-SANDBOX FINAL ARCHITECTURE

